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TROPHIC INTERACTIONS OF INVASIVE PHYTOPHAGOUS INSECTS WITH HOST PLANTS IN THE AGRO-LANDSCAPES OF THE FERGANA VALLEY

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Abstract

Based on field surveys conducted between 2022 and 2025 in different parts of the Fergana Valley, this study provides an ecological analysis of trophic interactions between invasive insects and their host plants. A total of 256 plant-invasive complex interactions were recorded across 24 plant families, 83 plant taxa and 26 invasive insect complexes. Invasive pressure was unevenly distributed among plant families, with a marked concentration in economically important crop groups. Functional guild analysis revealed the dominance of piercing-sucking phytophagous insects (43.4%), followed by leaf-feeding phytophages (24.6%) and stem/shoot borers (11.3%). Both broad polyphagous complexes and narrowly specialized trophic complexes (restricted to a single plant family) were identified. The results provide a scientific basis for improving monitoring systems, phytosanitary regulation and integrated pest management (IPM) strategies.

Keywords: invasive insect, plant, trophic niche, polyphagy.

Introduction

Biological invasion processes are among the global problems that directly affect the stability of agriculture and natural ecosystems. As a result of the expansion of international trade, transport, and economic relations, the movement of insects into new areas and their establishment there is accelerating (Zokirov, 2019). This, in turn, causes additional damage to trophic chains, phytosanitary status, and crop productivity in local agroecosystems (Paini et al., 2016; Early et al., 2016; Hulme, 2021; Bonnamour et al., 2021). Under the conditions of the Fergana Valley, the extensive areas under horticulture, vegetable production, and industrial crops naturally create a favorable trophic base for invasive phytophages.

The extent of damage caused by invasive insects largely depends on the breadth of their host spectrum and the diversity of trophic niches. Phytophages with a broad host range can persist in various plant families and may serve as a bridge between agrobiocenoses (Forister et al., 2015). Therefore, analyzing "plant-insect" trophic interactions using a network approach and assessing the functional structure of interactions are important for ecological interpretation (Ings et al., 2009).

From an applied perspective, such analyses support early detection of the impacts of invasive phytophages, improvement of monitoring systems, and development of integrated pest control measures. Integrated control measures envisage comprehensive management of harmful organisms not by a single method, but by taking into account agroecological conditions, the bioecology of the harmful organism, and economic injury levels (Kogan, 1998; Barzman et al., 2015).

This article presents the results of an ecological-theoretical analysis of trophic interactions between invasive insects and plants based on field materials collected from different areas of the valley.

Materials and Methods

The research material was prepared based on field observations and collected samples obtained in 2022-2025 in different areas of the Fergana Valley. The composition of the invasive entomofauna of the Fergana Valley was determined, and a total of 28 species were recorded (26 phytophagous species, 2 zoophagous species); however, given the quarantine significance of some species, the species list is not presented in the article. The analyses were conducted for 26 phytophages.

For each plant family, the number of recorded invasive complexes (the number of I codes) was calculated. This indicator served to assess the relative importance of a plant family as a “trophic resource area” for invasive phytophages.

Trophic niches were coded into 5-6 functional groups (guilds): G1 - leaf phytophages, G2 - piercing-sucking phytophages, G3 - phytophages associated with fruits, seeds, buds/flowers, and tubers, G4 - bark-cambium pests, G5 - stem and shoot pests, G6 - conifer phytophages. For each guild, the number of records and the share (%) were calculated.

The host range of invasive complexes was assessed by plant families: 1. Recorded in only one plant family; 2. Medium range - 2-4 families; 3. Five or more families. This classification was applied conditionally in accordance with theoretical approaches to diet breadth (Forister et al., 2015).

Plant taxa were divided into agro-typological groups: 1) fruit orchards, 2) vegetable-melon crops, 3) field and industrial crops, 4) ornamental plants and trees and shrubs. For each group, the number of families, the number of plant taxa, the number of invasive complexes, and the number of trophic interactions were calculated and compared using a plant-insect density indicator.

Results

Based on the obtained data, 24 plant families, 83 plant taxa, and 26 invasive insect complexes (I1-I26) were identified, and a total of 256 “plant-invasive complex” trophic interactions were recorded. These indicators made it possible to characterize the scale of the network (number of interactions) and the diversity of families and complexes.

Across plant families, the number of invasive complexes differed markedly (Table 1). The highest pressure was concentrated in families that are widely cultivated and have a relatively high number of taxa. In particular, Solanaceae (12 complexes), Rosaceae (11), Fabaceae (10), and Malvaceae (9). Notably, the share of interactions attributable to the Rosaceae and Solanaceae families accounted for 36.3% of all records (93/256 cases). This indicates that, in agrobiocenoses, the central component of invasive complexes is mainly associated with fruit orchard and vegetable crops.

For certain vegetable crops (e.g., tomato), 11 invasive complexes were recorded, and among fruit trees, 9 complexes each were identified on apple and pear. In some forage and industrial crops (e.g., alfalfa and cotton), the number of complexes was also high, which indicates the wide range of pathways for the spread of invasive pressure across the agro-landscape.

Table 1

Number of invasive complexes by plant families

Plant family	Plant taxa (n)	Invasive complexes (n)	Notes
Rosaceae	11	11	High invasive pressure; multiple trophic links.
Juglandaceae	1	5	Moderate; associated with several dominant complexes.

Plant family	Plant taxa (n)	Invasive complexes (n)	Notes
Vitaceae	1	3	Moderate; associated with several dominant complexes.
Poaceae	2	6	Moderate to high; contribution of polyphagous complexes is considerable.
Asteraceae	2	4	Moderate; associated with several dominant complexes.
Solanaceae	10	12	High invasive pressure; multiple trophic links.
Cucurbitaceae	4	7	Moderate to high; contribution of polyphagous complexes is considerable.
Fabaceae	6	10	High invasive pressure; multiple trophic links.
Brassicaceae	6	5	Moderate; associated with several dominant complexes.
Amaryllidaceae	1	1	Low; limited number of interactions (specific segment).
Amaranthaceae	2	2	Low; limited number of interactions (specific segment).
Moraceae	3	6	Moderate to high; contribution of polyphagous complexes is considerable.
Salicaceae	6	3	Moderate; associated with several dominant complexes.
Ulmaceae	2	4	Moderate; associated with several dominant complexes.
Rutaceae	5	5	Moderate; associated with several dominant complexes.

Plant family	Plant taxa (n)	Invasive complexes (n)	Notes
Lythraceae	1	2	Low; limited number of interactions (specific segment).
Cupressaceae	7	1	Dendro/conifer segment; narrow-range interactions predominate.
Pinaceae	2	1	Dendro/conifer segment; narrow-range interactions predominate.
Malvaceae	5	9	High invasive pressure; multiple trophic links.
Linaceae	1	1	Low; limited number of interactions (specific segment).
Sapindaceae	2	2	Low; limited number of interactions (specific segment).
Elaeagnaceae	1	1	Low; limited number of interactions (specific segment).
Pedaliaceae	1	1	Low; limited number of interactions (specific segment).
Apiaceae	1	1	Low; limited number of interactions (specific segment).

As a result of classifying trophic niches into functional groups, piercing-sucking phytophages (G2) were identified as dominant in the network structure (111 cases; 43.4%). The high share of this group indicates that a substantial part of invasive complexes spreads across different plants by sucking sap or feeding on plant juices. Leaf phytophages (G1) ranked second, with 63 cases (24.6%) recorded. Stem and shoot pests (G5) were observed in 29 cases (11.3%), while phytophages associated with fruits, seeds, buds/flowers, or tubers (G3) were recorded in 26 cases (10.2%). The bark-cambium segment (G4) comprised 18 cases (7.0%) and mainly reflects specialized interactions typical of trees and shrubs. Although interactions on conifers (G6) were limited to 9 cases (3.5%), they indicate a distinct direction of invasive pressure in green spaces and landscaping systems (Table 2).

Table 2
Distribution of trophic niches by functional guilds (n=256)

Guild	Description	Number of cases (n)	Share (%)
G1	Leaf phytophages (leaf feeders/miners)	63	24.6
G2	Piercing-sucking phytophages (sap suckers)	111	43.4
G3	Phytophages associated with fruits, seeds, buds/flowers, and tubers	26	10.2
G4	Bark-cambium pests (bark, cambium)	18	7.0
G5	Stem and shoot pests (stem/shoot)	29	11.3
G6	Conifer-segment phytophages (needle/twig segment)	9	3.5

When the host range of invasive complexes was assessed by plant families, 12 complexes occurred in five or more plant families and were conditionally classified as broadly polyphagous. Such polyphagous complexes may form a trophic bridge between different crop groups across the agro-landscape and may represent priority targets for monitoring. Within the obtained results, the single complex with the broadest range was recorded in 11 plant families and 26 plant taxa.

Conversely, 10 complexes occurred in only one plant family, forming a group of narrowly trophically specialized invasive complexes; such interactions are more likely to be associated with specialized trophic niches (e.g., conifers or the bark-cambium segment). The remaining 4 complexes were recorded within 2-4 families and were assigned to the medium-range group. Thus, the simultaneous presence of polyphagous and narrow-range complexes in the network structure indicates that invasive pressure consists of both “widely spreading” and “locally specialized” components.

When plants were divided into agro-typological groups, trophic interactions were most concentrated in the fruit orchard category (83 cases; 4.15 interactions/plant). The vegetable-melon (82 cases; 3.28 interactions/plant) and field and industrial crops (47 cases; 3.36 interactions/plant) groups also showed high interaction density, indicating that invasive pressure in cropping systems is intensified due to a broad trophic base.

In the category of ornamental trees and shrubs, although the number of plant taxa was high, the number of invasive complexes was relatively low (6 complexes) and interaction density was lower (44 cases; 1.83 interactions/plant) (Table 3). Without excluding the possibility that green spaces and ornamental species may serve as a “reservoir” of invasive pressure, this result indicates that the complexity of the trophic network (highly connected segments) is generally higher in agroecosystems.

Table 3.

Indicators of trophic interactions for categories of agricultural crops and ornamental trees and shrubs

Agrocenoses (crop groups)	Families (n)	Plant taxa (n)	Invasive complexes (n)	Interactions (n)	Density (interactions/plant)
Fruit orchards	6	20	14	83	4.15
Vegetable-melon crops	7	25	14	82	3.28
Field and industrial crops	6	14	11	47	3.36
Ornamental trees and shrubs	8	24	6	44	1.83

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate an uneven and differentiated structure of the trophic network associated with invasive phytophages in the agro-landscape of the Fergana Valley. The concentration of pressure at the level of plant families is primarily explained by the large resource base of economically widespread crops. Invasive organisms introduced through international trade and logistics channels often become established rapidly in human-created agroecosystems. This is because monocultures or limited crop assortments occupy large areas in such ecosystems and serve as a stable “trophic platform” for invaders (Hulme, 2021; Paine et al., 2016).

A second important aspect is the dominance of piercing-sucking phytophages in the trophic-niche structure. The high share of this group (43.4%) indicates that a substantial part of invasive complexes acquires resources by feeding on plant sap, piercing and sucking from the petiole, the lower leaf surface, or generative organs. Such phytophages are often characterized by small body size, rapid reproduction, and the ability to switch host plants. As a result, their early detection is critical in monitoring and phytosanitary control. Within an integrated control approach, combined measures (agrotechnical practices, biological and chemical control, quarantine) are considered a priority specifically for such “rapidly reproducing and multi-host” groups (Kogan, 1998; Barzman et al., 2015).

From the perspective of trophic network theory, broadly polyphagous complexes (more than five families) may function as “high-level nodes” that connect the network. Such nodes increase connectivity between plants and crop groups and accelerate the spatial spread of invasive pressure. Within the preliminary dataset, the recording of the broadest polyphagous complex in 11 families and 26 plant taxa suggests that limiting the management of invasive pressure in an agro-landscape to “only a single crop” may often be insufficient. Global analyses of diet breadth likewise show that polyphagy is widespread among many phytophages (Forister et al., 2015).

At the same time, the presence of a group of narrowly trophically specialized invasive complexes (10 complexes restricted to only one family) reflects a second-specialized-component of the network. Such interactions are often associated with narrow trophic niches, such as conifers or the bark-cambium segment, and their control may be more effective through “targeted monitoring” and plant-oriented preventive measures (removal of damaged branches, inspection of planting material).

A comparison across agricultural crops showed that the fruit orchard group had the highest interaction density. This result can be explained by the presence of perennial plants in orchard agroecosystems, the long phenological period, and the simultaneous availability of various vegetative and generative organs. The network is also relatively complex in the vegetable-melon and field/industrial crop groups, where rapid renewal of host plants and crop rotation during the season may provide invaders with a continuous resource. Although the number of invasive

complexes was lower in the ornamental trees and shrubs group, this does not theoretically exclude the possibility that this group may serve as a “reservoir” for agroecosystems (Blackburn et al., 2011; Ings et al., 2009).

The spatial and temporal unevenness of field observations may influence the structure of the results. Nevertheless, the table-based analysis shows in which plant families, which trophic niches, and which agro-groups invasive pressure accumulates, thereby providing a sufficient basis for fundamental theoretical conclusions.

Practical recommendations

The obtained results make it possible to substantiate the following general approaches for managing invasive phytophagous pressure (in particular, within monitoring and the IPM system):

- conduct monitoring regularly in “core families” and in agro-groups with high interaction density, and record the trophic niche (leaf, stem, fruit, etc.) separately during field observations;
- in cases where the likelihood of broadly polyphagous complexes is high, conduct monitoring not limited to a single crop, but jointly with adjacent crops and agro-landscape elements (field margins of vegetable-melon fields, green spaces);
- taking into account the high share of piercing-sucking phytophages, systematize early warning indicators and, where necessary, apply selected measures;
- within IPM, integrate agrotechnical measures (removal of plant residues, crop rotation, healthy planting material), biological control options, and, when needed, selected chemical methods;
- from a phytosanitary quarantine perspective, strengthen inspection and documentation in the movement of seedlings, seeds, fruit and vegetable products, and timber materials, and cooperate with authorized bodies regarding potentially quarantine-significant objects;
- regularly update the database, enter new records in standardized fields, and maintain electronic registration to enable analysis by time and space.

Conclusion

The results obtained on the basis of field materials collected in 2022-2025 from different parts of the Fergana Valley made it possible to provide a descriptive assessment of trophic interactions between invasive insects and plants. The dataset recorded 256 trophic interactions for 26 invasive complexes within 24 plant families and 83 plant taxa. Invasive pressure was uneven across families, and a high number of complexes was identified in certain economically important families. This indicates the dependence of invasion processes in agroecosystems on the resource base. When trophic niches were partitioned into functional guilds, piercing-sucking phytophages (43.4%) and leaf phytophages (24.6%) were identified as the leading components of the network. Broadly polyphagous complexes (more than five families) may be important as a connecting segment in the spread of invasive pressure across the agro-landscape. At the same time, the presence of a group of narrow-range, narrowly trophically specialized invasive complexes also requires a differentiated management approach. Comparison across agro-groups showed that interaction density was high in fruit orchards, vegetable-melon crops, and field and industrial cropping systems, whereas it was relatively lower in the ornamental trees and shrubs group. Based on these results, it is recommended to strengthen monitoring in core crop groups, apply IPM measures in an integrated manner, and establish management aligned with phytosanitary quarantine requirements.

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